

THE ROLE OF PREVENTATIVE HEALTH SCREENINGS IN CONTROLLING THE RISK FACTORS FOR DIFFERENT CHRONIC NON-COMMUNICATIVE DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Lifestyle, controlling the risk factors for developing chronic non-communicative diseases, and regular preventative health screenings are all elements needed for reducing the negative statistics for cardiovascular diseases and endocrine disorders in Bulgaria. This article presents the opinions of 417 people from all over the country who participated in a questionnaire between December 2022 and January 2023 on their self-evaluated health, lifestyle, risk factors, as well as on the frequency, initiative and mode of preventative health screenings. The results show there is a need for change in all directions, and for greater engagement by patients, medical specialists and by society as a whole.

Keywords: Lifestyle, risk factors, preventative health screenings, effectiveness.

Introduction

The lifestyle, controlling the risk factors for developing chronic non-communicative diseases, and regular preventative health screenings are all elements needed for reducing the negative statistics for cardiovascular and endocrine disorders in Bulgaria.

One of the ways to control the causes for chronic non-communicative diseases (NCD) is an annually conducted mandatory preventative health screening. The aim of these screenings is the early detection of deviations in the clinical and laboratory indicators and timely intervention by the medical specialists.

In Decree № 8 from 03.11.2016 on preventative health screening (with entry into force on 01.01.2017, issued by the Minister of Health, SG, issue 92, 22.11.2016; am. and add. SG, issue 48, 28.06.2022) defines the conditions, procedure and funding for preventative health screenings for early disease detection. The prophylactic screenings and tests are done in accordance with the medical standards and the rules for proper medical practice.

The goal of this article is to present the patients' position on the role of preventative health screenings in controlling the risk factors for chronic non-communicative diseases in our country.

To realise this goal, the following tasks were drafted:

1. Health, lifestyle and present risk factor self-evaluation of the respondents
2. An analysis of the frequency, initiative and mode of the preventative health screenings according to the participants.

A direct questionnaire survey was conducted using the online platform Google Forms among 417 Bulgarian citizens – health-insured persons (HIP) over the age of 18, during a two-month period (December 2022 – January 2023). Descriptive and analytical statistical methods were used.

ANALYSIS

Out of the survey participants, 65.5% (273) are women and 34.5% (144) are men. The average age of the participants is 46, whereby the employed are the majority – 76% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Participants by social status

When asked about their education, the largest portion of participants reported completing secondary education – 36.7 % (157), followed by those with higher education – Masters’ Degree - 34.8% (145), Bachelors’

Degree - 13.2% (55) and Professional Bachelor’s - 6% (25).

Income is one of the factors influencing lifestyle and medical service consumption. The distribution of the participants by their income is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Participants by their monthly income

In social research, self-assessment of health status (SRH - self-rated health) is used to assess the health status. In multiple studies, this approach has proven that self-assessment is a good measure not only of this status (Mandrcbacka, et al. 1998; Martikainen, et al. 1999; Singh-Manoux, et al. 2006) but also a predictor of mortality, which may be used just like the other risk factors, especially when it comes to adults (Benyamini, Idler 1999; Idler, Benyamini 1997; Burstrom, 23 Fredlund 2001; DE Salvo, et al. 2006; McFadden, et al. 2009; Singh-Manoux, et al. 2007).

The European Health Interview is a part of the European health research system, which aims to use a harmonized toolbox, which would provide greater data

comparability between the EU member states. The Interview allows for assessing the EU population’s health status, lifestyle (health determinants) and use of health services. It was ran in three waves – 2008, 2014, 2019, and according to the results of all three, over 65% of the participants assess their health as “good” or “very good”. According to Eurostat data, from “European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions” in 2019, 71.5% of men and 67.2% of women in the EU member states consider their health “very good” or “good”, which corresponds to the larger-scale self-rated health research mentioned above.

Figure 3. The participants by self-rated health

Lifestyle is a factor influencing people’s health and their medical service consumption. To the question “How would you evaluate your lifestyle?” (Figure 4) over half of the participants give a positive answer – 50.8% assess their lifestyle as “mostly healthy”, while 9.1% as “healthy”. Almost a third (29.7%) of the respondents would describe their lifestyle as “mostly unhealthy”, while 4.3% as “unhealthy”. As little as 6%

say they cannot determine. The presence of negative answers to this question is a positive sign, since it shows that there are people who realise they do not live a healthy lifestyle. This awareness and the help of medical specialists can aid them in changing their way of life for the better.

Figure 4. The respondent’s self-assessment of their lifestyle

In relation to lifestyle, the respondents were also asked about their risk factors. The results show that the largest relative share of the participants – 47.7%, list low physical activity as a risk factor in their life. In second place, the respondents put unhealthy eating (38.8%), followed by tobacco smoking at 36% and alcohol consumption at 23%. As little as 17% of the participants report that none of these risk factors are present in their lives. The sum of the percentages is over

100 since the respondents had the opportunity to indicate more than one health risk factor that’s present in their lives. The health risk indicators are a matter of behavior and may be reduced or fully eliminated by the patients’ willpower and eagerness, on one hand, and with the GP’s help, on the other hand. The fact that those risk factors are indicated and recognized as such is also a good sign that the need for change is also recognized.

Figure 5. The risk factors present in the participants' lives

Prophylaxis is one of the methods for controlling risk factors and preventing the occurrence and development of chronic non-communicative diseases. In our country it is predominantly realized by conducting annual preventative health screenings by a GP. We asked the participants about how often they have had a preventative health screening with tests done by their GP (Figure 6). The largest portion of the respondents - 52.8% (220), indicate that they have had such an exam carried out on an yearly basis, while 18.2% indicate that they have had a preventative health screening with tests done every other year. There is a not insignificant number of respondents who say that they have had a preventative health screening done once every three years - 14.9%, while 5.5% respond that they have never had such an exam, and 8.6% of the respondents cannot answer the question. Therefore, it follows that 1/3 of the participants (29%) do not practice adequate prophylaxis, which is a prerequisite for developing chronic

non-communicative diseases. This is most probably caused by the fact that the main initiative for preventative health screenings is left to the patients, as indicated by most of the respondents- 58.9% (Figure 7). According to 31.2% of the participants, preventative health screenings are initiated by the GP, while a very small portion point to another physician (4.6%) or an employer (3.3%) as the main initiator. Based on the obtained results one can conclude that there are changes needed to motivate patients to have their annual preventative health screenings (for example, using the media, advertisements and digital technology), on one hand, and introducing measures (penalties and incentives respectively) among the population, aiming to have those screening happen on a larger scale. It is also necessary to provide a detailed explanation of the importance and significance of these preventative health screenings in GP's offices, as well as in public spaces like schools, universities and in the work environment.

Figure 6. Participants by the frequency of preventative health screenings

Figure 7. Initiative for carrying out a preventative health screening according to the respondents.

55.6% of the respondents report that they have had additional preventative health screening performed by someone other than their GP. Most often this was a paid health screening and tests - 56.9% of the participants, followed by a screening though an Occupational Health Service (OHS) - 19.8% and by an insurer – 15.1%. The regulated prophylactic screenings performed by the GP are limited depending on the patient’s age, and those by

OHS by the working conditions, which is probably why over half of the respondents report paying for a preventative health screening with tests. From the responses, it becomes clear that a not insignificant portion of the participants use and take advantage of preventative health screenings by OHS and voluntary health insurance.

Figure 8. Mode of preventative health screening according to the respondents

CONCLUSION

We can draw the following conclusions from the results presented

1. 77.2% of the respondents rate their health as “very good” or “good”, which corresponds to large-scale research in health self-assessment.
2. Almost a third (29.7%) of the respondents rate their lifestyle as “mostly unhealthy”, while 4.3% rate it as “unhealthy”, which indicates they are aware of the present problem and the need for subsequent corrective measures.

3. The respondents indicate that low physical activity (47.7%), unhealthy eating (38.8%), tobacco smoking (36%) and alcohol consumption (23%) are risk factors present in their lives.

4. Over half of the participants (52.8%) have yearly preventative health screening done by their GP, whereas the initiative is mostly personal (59.5%) or the GP’s in 1/3 (31.2%).

5. Paid preventative health screening and tests – 56.9%, screenings by OHS - 19.8%, or by an insurer -

15.1%, are other modes of preventative health screening among the participants.

All said so far proves that a not insignificant portion of the respondents need a change in their lifestyle and the control over risk factors for developing chronic non-communicative diseases. On the other hand, the fact the participants give those answers shows that the patients are aware of the problem. The needed measures should be taken with the population's personal initiative, but should also include engaging the medical specialists and society as a whole. There needs to be a larger degree of engagement by the GPs and other medical specialists in initiating preventative health screenings. This can happen by providing detailed explanation of the importance and significance of these preventative health screenings.

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